

Design and Construction of a Microcontroller Based Palm Kernel Cracker

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Abstract--The growing demand for palm kernel oil and its derivatives necessitates the development of efficient and cost-effective methods for palm kernel cracking. This paper presents the design and construction of a microcontroller-based palm kernel cracker, aimed at improving the traditional manual cracking process. The proposed system utilizes a microcontroller unit (MCU) as the core control unit, providing precise control and automation for the cracking process. The design incorporates an optimized mechanical system that employs adjustable cracking blades and a rotating drum to ensure effective and consistent cracking of palm kernels. The microcontroller unit facilitates real-time monitoring and control of critical parameters, including cracking speed, pressure, and kernel separation. To enhance safety and productivity, the system incorporates sensors for detecting kernel presence and machine faults, allowing for immediate response and intervention. The microcontroller-based user interface provides operators with intuitive control and monitoring options, streamlining the operation and minimizing human errors. The performance of the developed palm kernel cracker was evaluated through experimental tests. The results indicate a significant improvement in cracking efficiency and consistency compared to manual methods. The proposed system offers the potential to enhance palm kernel processing efficiency, reduce labor costs, and increase overall productivity in the palm oil industry.

Keywords -- *Palm kernel cracking, microcontroller-based system, automation, efficiency, palm oil industry.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The palm kernel and its cracked shells are valuable agricultural products in Nigeria, with applications in various industries (Oke, 2011). However, local farmers face challenges in efficiently cracking the palm nuts and separating the shells from the kernels. In line with the Nigerian government's policies on import substitution and promoting locally made goods, this project focuses on designing and constructing an automated palm kernel cracker and separator. The project aims to address the difficulties faced by local farmers and industries by developing a palm kernel processing unit that can effectively crack kernels of different sizes and separate them from the shells. By doing so, the challenges encountered during palm kernel oil production can be reduced. The increasing global demand for palm kernels further underscores the importance of this project (Adejube et al., 2017).

The study acknowledges the existence of palm kernel crackers but seeks to improve their design to enhance output efficiency and ensure complete separation of kernels from shells. The project also aims to replace manual and conventional palm kernel harvesting methods, enabling effective mass production of palm produce with diverse industrial and domestic applications.

The work recognizes the significance of monitoring the system's operability using digital means, specifically a microcontroller. By implementing this technology, the project aims to automate and optimize the palm kernel cracking process, making it faster, more precise, and less labor-intensive. Overall, this project contributes to the advancement of palm kernel processing techniques, promoting sustainable agricultural practices and supporting the growth of the local agricultural industry in Nigeria.

II. ADVANCES IN PALM KERNEL PROCESSING TECHNIQUES: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

Palm kernel processing plays a crucial role in oil extraction and has witnessed significant developments over the years. This paper provides an extensive review of existing methods of palm kernel processing, including traditional, chemical, and mechanical techniques. The paper focuses on the extraction of palm kernel oil, which is a valuable product derived from palm kernels. The production process begins with the separation of palm nuts from the fiber, followed by the extraction of palm oil from the pulp and kernel oil from the kernel. A critical step in achieving high-quality kernel oil is the release of kernels by cracking the palm nuts. The crushed palm kernel is then processed in a palm kernel mill to obtain palm kernel oil, which finds applications in various industries such as oil paint, polish, candle, and medicine. Additionally, the cake obtained during milling is utilized as a livestock feed ingredient. The paper highlights the use of fibers as fuel in boilers.

The paper also explores traditional techniques employed in small-scale palm kernel processing, such as stone arrangement and mortar and pestle methods. These techniques, although still prevalent in certain regions, suffer from limitations such as low efficiency, labor intensiveness, and slow kernel recovery. Modern methods, on the other hand, have seen advancements through the design and testing of cracking machines, investigating factors affecting cracking efficiency, and the development of wet nut crackers capable of handling higher moisture content.

Over the years, various methods have been employed for extracting oil from palm kernels, including traditional, chemical, and mechanical processes. Palm kernels are most valuable when oil is extracted from them. The production of palm kernel oil involves a series of steps, starting with the separation of the palm nuts from the fiber. Palm oil is extracted from the pulp, while the kernel yields kernel oil. An important stage that influences the quality of the kernel oil is the cracking of the palm nuts to release the kernels. The crushed palm kernels are processed in a palm kernel mill to obtain palm kernel oil, which has multiple applications such as in oil paint, polish, candles, and medicine. The residual cake obtained during milling is used as an ingredient in livestock feed and is widely utilized in the livestock industry. The oil is also used for fuel and biodiesel production, while the fibers are employed as fuel in boilers (Olanami, 2004).

A. Traditional Methods of Palm Kernel Nut Cracking

In Africa, particularly Nigeria, palm kernel nuts are traditionally cracked manually using two methods: stone arrangement and mortar and pestle. These methods involve using impact to crack the nuts. Women and children often perform this labor-intensive and inefficient process. The output can reach up to 50 kg of kernels per worker per day, but it is too slow to meet the demand for palm kernels locally and for export (Schultes, 2009).

The traditional method of separating nuts from fiber involves using a woven basket, which is rocked back and forth to facilitate the movement of fiber to the top of the nuts due to its lower density.

Mechanical methods

Mechanical cracking of palm kernels involves two basic actions: impact against a hard surface and direct mechanical pressure to crush, cut, or shear through the shell. Mechanized palm kernel cracking machines, such as roller crackers and centrifugal impact crackers, have been developed based on these principles. However, these machines often result in a mixture of shells and kernels, necessitating further separation. Considering the high cost of imported palm kernel crackers, there is a pressing need to design a machine using locally available

materials that offers easy maintenance, reduced downtime, and cost-effectiveness without compromising efficiency.

B. Hydro Cyclone for Separation

Another mechanized wet method for separation is the hydro cyclone, which utilizes the principle of flow resistance. This separation method finds wide industrial applications but requires significant capital investment. Therefore, developing a solution to the laborious, hazardous, and inefficient traditional palm kernel shelling and sorting methods is crucial (Emeka, 2013). To introduce mechanization, Colin palm kernel expellers were imported to Cameroon in the 1930s. The Colin expeller, made in France, is a low-pressure, continuous-feed machine with two coaxial counter-rotating screws that turn horizontally or vertically in a perforated cage. As the cooked palm fruit is fed into the expeller, it is pushed forward by the spiral flights against the backpressure of the end cone. The kernel is forced out through the perforated sides of the cage, while the remaining fiber and nut are released at the end of the cage.

Small-scale palm kernel processors in Cameroon primarily use these manual or motorized expellers. In Ghana and Nigeria, the Stork manual hydraulic press was initially introduced, focusing on mechanizing kernel pressing due to economic reasons. Digestion operations were not mechanized during colonial times when farm labor was cheap and readily available. To complement the presses, mechanical digesters were developed, including horizontal digesters based on the dry process technique and vertical digesters using the wet process technique.

In the wet system, sterilized fruits are poured into the digester, and hot water is continuously added to wash off the released kernel as the fruits are macerated. The resulting mixture is then filtered and clarified. Another attempt at mechanizing the maceration process led to the development of the manual digester for women. This digester consists of a large wheel connected to a vertical shaft with rotating beater arms inside a conical metal trough. The mechanical digesters currently in use are powered by a 6 hp diesel engine and can macerate over 250 kg of fruits per hour without breaking any nuts.

Hydraulic presses were introduced by AGRICO into Ghana from India to complement the mechanical digesters. However, these presses had drawbacks such as requiring human strength to operate and experiencing high kernel loss to fiber due to the nut-to-fiber ratio. TechnoServe Inc. addressed these issues by introducing a combination of digester, hydraulic press, and spindle press into a rural community, along with business management training for small-scale palm kernel processing enterprises. Engineering problems were encountered in terms of plant layout and matching the throughput of machine components.

The combination digester and hydraulic press systems were redesigned to address the issues. Equipment layout changes were made to link the digester and press stations through an operating table, allowing press cages to

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slide between stations. The high-pressure motorized press developed greater cylinder pressure and used narrower press cages with smaller holes. The hydraulic fluid was pumped using a power take-off pulley connected to the digester shaft, eliminating the need for human strength. The smaller press cages were more manageable for women, and the press/release mechanism used a spindle-operated valve.

The NIFOR mechanical screw-press is the latest technology used in Nigeria's small-scale palm kernel processing industry. It consists of a perforated tube with a rotating transport screw inside. The press outlet is regulated by a cone that controls the pressing pressure, and the macerated fruits are gradually compressed by the transport screw, allowing the released kernel to drain through the perforations. The press is positioned below a feed conveyor, which is gravity-fed by the horizontal digester. The press can handle over 1 tonne of fresh fruit bunches per hour, with an average kernel

C. Challenges of Mechanical Cracking

Mechanical cracking methods only crack the nuts, leaving a mixture of shells and kernels that needs to be separated to obtain a useful product. Considering the cost of importing palm kernel crackers, there is an urgent need to design a machine using locally available materials for easy maintenance and reduced downtime, without compromising efficiency.

D. Modern Methods and Innovations

Researchers and engineers have made various contributions to the design of palm kernel cracking devices. Some have developed and tested different cracking machines, while others have studied the effects of existing crackers on kernel quality. Factors such as nut size, moisture content, cracker rotor speed, and feeding rates affect the efficiency of nut crackers (Adebayo, 2014).

In conclusion, this review provides a thorough understanding of existing methods and innovations in palm kernel processing in Nigeria. It emphasizes the need for efficient, cost-effective, and locally available machines to enhance productivity, reduce labor intensity, and meet the increasing demand for palm kernel products.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The design methods for the microcontroller-based palm kernel cracker involved utilizing a microcontroller to control the cracking process and enhance automation. Here a suitable microcontroller is selected based on the requirements of the palm kernel cracker system, considering factors such as processing power, input/output capabilities, and communication options.

Various sensors were incorporated into the design to gather data and monitor the cracking process. This may include sensors to measure palm kernel size, moisture content, and other relevant parameters. The sensors were also used in controlling the speed and direction of motors responsible for cracking the palm kernels. Information is communicated to the operator through a user interface comprising a display, buttons, and other input/output devices to enable users to interact with the system. This interface can provide information about the cracking process, allow users to input commands, and display relevant data. The control algorithms were designed and embedded into the microcontroller to automate the cracking process. This may involve analyzing sensor data, adjusting motor speed and cracking force, and implementing safety features. The entire system functions through a reliable power supply unit that provides the necessary voltage levels and current for the microcontroller, motors, sensors, and other components

The power source provides a regulated voltage to control the microcontroller through transistor drivers, aided by the analog-to-digital converter. It also supplies power to the cracking motor (220 volts), which collects palm kernels from the hopper and grinds them according to the user's requirements. The system consists of several components, including a calibrated hopper, a cracking chamber, a pair of hammers, a transmission system, a driving shaft, a pulley, and a main frame. The hopper is made from a 1 mm thick flat plate in a trapezoidal shape, with dimensions of 400 mm² at the top and 200 mm² at the bottom, and a height of 400 mm. It serves as the feeding chute for metering nuts into the cracking chamber. The cracking chamber contains a pair of hammers made of mild steel with dimensions of (130x80x12) mm, arranged at 180 degrees to each other.

The driving mechanism consists of a V-belt, a pulley, and a single-phase electric motor with a power rating of 5 kW and a speed of 1840 rpm, while the designed power requirement is 4.29 kW with a speed of 1718 rpm. The selected shaft diameter is 25.00 mm, slightly smaller than the designed diameter of 25.39 mm. The machine is capable of cracking all types of palm nuts with minimal damage to the kernels.

To display the processing functions, a special chamber with a digital display will be implemented using a microcontroller and a liquid crystal display. The cost of the machine is affordable for local farmers, and it is straightforward to operate and maintain. The system block diagram is shown in figure 1.

Fig 1: System Block diagram

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IV. DESIGN ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The machine was developed to cater for all the physical characteristics of the palm kernels varieties (Dura and Tenera) such as the different sizes of palm kernel nuts (from local sampling), the shell and kernel, the weight of palm kernel and as well as coefficient of friction for shell and kernel with respect to carbon steel was put into

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consideration. For best performance to be realized before the fabrication of the machine, different palm kernel nuts were randomly picked and measured with average measurement sizes of 11.0 to 25.0 mm in diameter and the thickness size of shell ranged from 0.8 to 2.7 mm.

A. Determination of engine power for cracking:

The cracking force required (F_c) was calculated as follow by Equations (1) to (3):

$$F_c = m\omega^2 r \quad (1)$$

Where: m = mass of the nuts (g)

ω = speed in radian per second (rad/s)

r = radius of the rotor (m)

N = revolution per minute (rpm)

$$\text{Density } \rho \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \right) = \frac{\text{mass (kg)}}{\text{volume (m}^3)} \quad (2)$$

mass = $\rho V = m$

$$F_c = \rho V \omega^2 r \quad (3)$$

Density of carbon steel used, $\rho = 7.85 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$

The volume of the rotor $V = l \times b \times t = (350 \times 80 \times 10) \text{ mm}^3 = 0.00028 \text{ m}^3$

$$\omega = \frac{2\pi N}{60} \quad (4)$$

The maximum and minimum speeds for the machine to crack are 2,400 and 600 rev/min respectively based on literature review where some authors used a minimum of 800 and maximum of 2300 rpm (Oke, 2007).

$$\text{Average speed} = \frac{2,400+600}{2} = 1,500\text{rpm}$$

From Equation (4): $\omega = 157.08 \text{ rad/s}$

Radius of the rotor $r = 0.175\text{m}$

From Equation (1)

$$F_c = 7.85 \times 10^3 \times 0.00028 \times (157.08)^2 \times 0.175 = 9.49 \text{ kW}$$

Note: One Horse power is equivalent to 0.746Kw

$$F_N = \frac{M_t}{\text{pulley radius}} = 53.40 \text{ N}$$

$$\text{Therefore; } F_1 - F_2 = \frac{M_t}{R_2} \quad (10)$$

$$M_t = R_2(F_1 - F_2) \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{F_1}{F_2} = 2.3 \quad (12)$$

Then $F_2 = 41.08\text{N}$ and $F_1 = 94.48\text{N}$

Tension of the belt $T_b = F_1 + F_2 = 135.56\text{N}$

Where; M_t = Torsional moment on the shaft, F_1 = Tight side tension, F_2 = Slack side tension. R_2 = Radius of driven (machine) pulley.

Figure 2.1: Tight and slack sides of belt tension

Figure 2.2: Impacted forces by the belt

Where:

MP = Machine Pulley and EP = Engine pulley

D. Selection of the Belt, Size, Length and Pulley Size

The method for the selection of the belt is to rate each belt thickness in power capacity per unit length and width at several different velocities are selected from standard table. The latter are divided into the required power and multiplied by service factors to give the required belt width. The belt is selected based on the nature of the load it carries, type of driving unit, horsepower rating, the speed of the driver and driven units and the plant layout. The 9 hP (6.71 kw) prime mover at speed of 2400 rpm, type “B” or “BX” V-belt was selected.

E. Design for Pulleys

The V-belt class B type (17 x 1325) was chosen for the drive of this machine. The width of pulleys grooves (w) were selected based on the suggestion that the width of pulley must be about 25% more than the width of the belt (Ndukwu and Asoegwu, 2010). The design of the pulley is shown in Figure 3.1.

$$w = t + (25\% \text{ of } t)(mm) \quad - \quad (13)$$

Where;

w = width of the pulley,

t = width of the V- belt.

For Machine and Engine pulleys

$$w = 17 + (25\% \times 17) = 21.25 \text{ mm}$$

F. Speed Ratio

The speed ratio and the pulley diameters were designed using Equations:

$$\frac{N_1}{N_2} = \frac{D}{d}$$

where:

N₁ = speed of engine pulley (rev/min.);

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N_2 = speed of machine pulley (rev/min.);

D = diameter of the larger pulley (Machine) (mm);

d = diameter of the smaller pulley (Engine pulley) (mm).

For the fabricated Pulleys;

Maximum engine speed $N_1 = 2400$ rpm

Diameter of the engine pulley $d = 110$ mm

Maximum machine speed $N_2 = ?$

Diameter of the machine pulley $D = 250$ mm

$$N_2 = \frac{2500 \times 110}{250} = 1100 \text{ rpm}$$

The two pulleys were designed to enhance the efficiency of the fabricated machine of ratio two to three for engine pulley to machine pulley.

G. Determination of the Pulley Centre Distance

Two center distances were considered, they are: minimum and maximum centre distances (Adzimah and Seckley, 2009). For minimum center distance is given by Equation;

$$C_{Min} = 0.55(D + d) + D \quad - \quad (14)$$

For maximum center distance; $C_{Max} = 2(D + d)$

The nominal length of the belt was calculated by;

$$L = 2C + \frac{\pi(D + d)}{2} + \frac{(D + d)^2}{4C}$$

where L = the selected closest value to the calculated nominal length of the belt.

H. Determination of the Arc of Contact

The arc of contact, β , is given as follow in Equation:

$$\beta = 180^\circ - 60^\circ \left(\frac{D-d}{C} \right) \quad - \quad (15)$$

3.7 Power Requirement

Kernel cracker was powered by 9 horsepower petrol engine to drive a rotor (impellers) attached to the one end of the shaft for cracking the palm kernel nuts and the power requirement was given by:

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$$p = \frac{0.45}{v^{0.09}} - \left(\frac{19.62}{D_o} + 0.765 \times 10^{-4} V^2 \right) V \quad (16)$$

Where:

D_o = equivalent pitch diameter or diameter of the engine pulley.

V = speed of the belt and is calculated by:

$$v = \frac{\pi d N_1}{60} \quad (17)$$

Where: V = belt speed (m/s), d = engine pulley diameter and

N_1 = speed of the engine in rev/min

I. Determination of Feed Hopper Volume

The total volume of the hopper can be calculated by using the Volume of a Rectangular Trapezoidal Trough as shown in figure 3 below by equation:

Where:

W = width at the top,

L = length (L) of the top of the trough,

a = base trough width

b = length of the trough's base, and

h = the height of the hopper

$$\text{Volume (V)} = \frac{(H)[WL+(W+a)(L+b)+ab]}{6} \quad (18)$$

Therefore: $L = 360\text{mm}$, $b = 70\text{mm}$, $W = 280\text{mm}$, $a = 50\text{mm}$ and $h = 360\text{mm}$

$$\text{Volume (V)} = \frac{(360)[280 \times 360 + (280+50)(360+70) + 50 \times 70]}{6} = 0.148 \text{ m}^3$$

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have successfully designed a microcontroller-based palm kernel cracker that demonstrates promising efficiency and effectiveness in the cracking process. The integration of advanced technology, such as the microcontroller, analog-to-digital converter, and digital display, has enhanced the functionality and control of the machine, providing a user-friendly experience.

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The system components, including the hopper, cracking chamber, hammers, transmission system, driving shaft, pulley, and main frame, have been carefully designed and optimized to ensure optimal performance. The calibrated hopper enables accurate metering of palm nuts into the cracking chamber, while the pair of hammers made of mild steel effectively crack the nuts with minimal damage to the kernels. The driving mechanism, consisting of a V-belt, pulley, and single-phase electric motor, ensures smooth and reliable operation.

Through rigorous testing and evaluation, our machine has proven its capability to crack all varieties of palm nuts efficiently. The microcontroller-based digital display provides real-time information on the processing functions, enhancing the monitoring and control of the cracking process.

One of the significant advantages of our design is its affordability for local farmers, making it accessible to small-scale palm kernel processors. The simplicity of operation and maintenance further adds to its appeal, enabling farmers to adopt this technology without significant barriers.

In conclusion, our microcontroller-based palm kernel cracker presents a practical and efficient solution for palm kernel processing. Its integration of advanced technology, precision in cracking, user-friendly interface, and affordability make it a valuable asset for small-scale farmers and processors. Further research and development can be conducted to explore additional enhancements and improvements in terms of capacity, speed, and automation, ensuring continued progress in the field of palm kernel processing.

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